

Norms of gymnasiums and activities of gymnasiums.

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***Atiation :** Physical in education gymnastics separately place holds , this common physical development and of a person basic movement skills improve provides . gymnastics to himself special problems the most successful solution to do for wide satisfactions which creates different different exercises with separate stands _ Pedagogical tasks . Various gymnastics types according to training solution to do help will give the most important from tasks one physical preparation is to provide physical and spiritual power perfect developed strong young generation _*

***Key word :** Gymnastics , hoops , rings , trampoline , gymnastics carpet*

Gymnastics is it special selected physical exercises system health improve , harmonize physical education and human ability to move , his tip , dexterity , speed , endurance , flexibility in raising applied exercises , methodical methods .

Gymnastics includes several types of all-around. These include: for men - floor exercises, pommel horse exercises, rings, uneven bars, horizontal bar, vault; for women - support, exercises on uneven bars, balance beam and floor exercises. Rhythmic gymnastics includes artistic gymnastics, choreography, acrobatics. Gymnastics is an Olympic sport. The gymnastics federation is leading its development in our country

Hygienic requirements and rules of operation for gyms

Gymnastics classes are usually held in specially equipped gymnasiums. Gyms require utility rooms for equipment, rooms for trainers and teachers, locker rooms (men's, women's), as well as showers and toilets (toilets). Hygienic requirements for using halls

1. The decoration of the hall and its auxiliary rooms should be easy to clean.
2. Heaters are covered with a grill.
3. The temperature in the hall is 18-20 ° C (humidity - 50-60%).
4. Ventilation is natural and artificial.
5. The light area of the windows is at least 1/5 of the floor area.
6. All buildings should be cleaned regularly.

2.2. Characteristics of gymnastics equipment and auxiliary equipment The following equipment and sports equipment are used in gymnastics classes.

1. Gymnastic wall is used for performing general developmental exercises and climbing. Its height is 3 m 20 cm, width is 100 cm.

It is used for balancing, emphasis, lifting, etc., in individual and group trainings, as well as for relaxation of the participants. Its length is 4 m, width - 24 cm, height - 30 cm. A 5 cm wide block is installed at the bottom of the bench. When the gymnastic bench is turned upside down, you can perform balance exercises from this block.

3. Climbing ropes are hung on ceiling beams or special consoles. The thickness of the rope is 6-9 cm, the length is 4-6 m. It should be easy to hold it with your hands.

4. Rings are usually attached to special consoles. The height at which the rings are attached is 5 m 50 cm, the width between the rings is 50 cm, the height of the rings from the floor is 2 m 5 cm, the diameter of the rings is 18-19 cm.

5. Men's fences (parallel): length of poles - 3 m 50 cm, oval - 41-51 mm, height - 1 m 60 cm - 1 m 70 cm.

6. Women's parallel bars (uneven heights): the height of the lower pole is 1 m 30 cm - 1 m 50 cm, the height of the upper pole is 2 m 40 cm. The bars are reinforced with guy wires.

7. A gymnastic balance beam is used to perform balance exercises. The length of the log is 5 m, width 10 cm, height 1 m 20 cm, thickness 16 cm. For initial training and warm-up, a low log installed at a height of 50 cm from the floor is used. .

8. Jumping horse: height (women) – 1 m 10 cm – 1 m 20 cm, height (men) – 1 m 10 cm – 1 m 35 cm, width – 36 cm, length – 1 m 60 cm .

9. Horse for a swing: length - 1 m 60 cm, width - 36 cm, height - 1 m 20 cm, width between handles - 4-44 cm, handle height - 12 cm.

10. Gymnastics goat: height - 100-160 cm, length - 60 cm, height (thickness) - 40 cm.

11. Sneakers: length – 2 m 40 cm, height – 1 m 20 cm – 2 m 55 cm, neck diameter – 28–29 cm.

12. The gymnastic bridge is used for exercises on supports, balance beams and uneven bars; length - 1 m 20 cm, width - 60 cm, height - 16-20 cm.

13. Trampoline: length - 1 m 20 cm - 1 m 30 cm, height - 40-50 cm.

14. Gymnastics mats: length - 200 cm, width - 1 m 20 cm, thickness - 60-65 mm. When learning more complex exercises, use foam mats.

15. The floor exercise area (12-12 ×m) is demarcated by a white line, behind which a margin of at least 1 m is required.

16. Trampoline: length - 5 m, width - 2 m 50 cm, height - 1 m 20 cm.

Sports equipment

1. Gymnastics sticks: diameter 25–30 mm, length 90–110 cm.

2. Medicine balls: diameter 31-41 cm, weight 1-5 kg.
3. Dumbbells can be of different shapes, their weight is 1-5 kg.
4. Judges' indicators are intended to indicate points for performing exercises.
5. Rhythmic gymnastics equipment: jump ropes, ribbons, balls, hoops, sticks, etc.

From gyms send rules and equipment

Those who exercise in the gym must follow the following rules:

- 1) treat equipment and supplies with care, skillfully prepare them for classes, and then clean them;
- 2) treat magnesium with care, and at the end of the training, students should clean the post, parallel fence posts, rings, horse handles from magnesium and wipe the mats with a damp cloth;
- 3) to be in the hall only in sports clothes and shoes;
- 4) strictly follow the instructions of the teacher (trainer) during the lessons, help your friends;
- 5) study safety rules, self-insurance methods;
- 6) entering and exiting the hall is possible only with the teacher's permission.

It is recommended to check the gym equipment daily and correct any problems found immediately. A detailed inspection of the shells should be carried out once a month.

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